

GENERAL COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES

in Diamond Open Access publishing

Multimedia

Engage a wider audience by presenting research in accessible and engaging formats. Develop video abstracts, podcasts, infographics that summarise key findings and attract readers beyond traditional academic circles.

Webinars

Foster deeper understanding and engagement by hosting live or recorded webinars featuring authors discussing their work. This provides a platform for direct interaction with the audience and encourages broader dissemination of research insights.

Academic events

Organise and participate in academic events to raise publications' profile within the relevant academic communities.

Cross-journal promotion

Expand your readership and influence by cross-promoting articles in related journals. Collaborate on joint special issues or thematic series to reach a wider audience across different disciplines and foster interdisciplinary dialogue.

Interactions with readers

Cultivate a strong relationship with your readership through interactive content such as surveys and feedback forms. Understanding their interests and needs allows you to tailor the journal's content and improve its overall quality and relevance.